

Phenomenological modeling attempt to explain gravity and propagation of electromagnetic/light waves

Summary:

The ideas presented in this article leads to a physical model in which a three-dimensional and dynamic flow of "ether" plays the role of both a support for the propagation of electromagnetic and light waves as well as a source of gravitational effects. In this framework, the ether flows centripetally towards the center of masses and interacts locally with atomic structures (causing reflections, diffractions and refractions of the waves). This approach offers, for example, an alternative interpretation of the redshift of starlight, gravitational lenses or quantum coherence, without resorting to the notion of photon-particle.

Introduction:

As a preamble, I would like to point out that I have a deep and sincere respect and admiration for the physicists who have mathematically formalized the theories in force in the physical field: I do not in any way question the accuracy of their work but I do try to give a physical meaning to their experiments and calculations.

Ever since I discovered the genesis of special relativity in preparatory classes at Louis le Grand School a long time ago, I have felt a kind of frustration with the phenomenological understanding of the Michelson and Morley experiment that potentially allowed Einstein's genius to mathematically formalize the theory of relativity. Thus, the propagation of waves without support or the supposed existence of particles of zero mass like photons has always deeply hampered my physical intuition.

Looking back at Michelson and Morley's experiment:

When in 1887 Michelson and Morley found that the speed of sunlight perceived on Earth remained the same whether the Earth's rotation moved us closer to the Sun or further away from it, it was commonly accepted by the scientific community of the time that there could not exist a "luminiferous ether" that could be used to propagate light (because in this case there would have to be an addition or subtraction of the respective speeds of light and Earth).

Einstein therefore affirmed that the speed of light must always be the same and deduced the Lorentz equations, the mathematical and fundamental bases of the theory of special and then general relativity.

However, it must be kept in mind that the Michelson and Morley experiment aimed above all to know if there existed an static medium for light propagation, the famous luminiferous ether... The interpretation of the (indisputable) results of their experiment could therefore also result in the questioning of this hypothesis and not by the absence of a propagation medium.

Let us now suppose that this ether is not immobile but in motion, more precisely that it moves with the earth in a global rotational movement in three dimensions: In this case, the relative movement between the earth and this propagation medium is zero, it no longer depends on the relative movement of the earth with respect to the sun and this would explain why Michelson and Morley

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measured the same speed of propagation of light in this medium, whatever the rotation of the earth in its orbit around the sun.

The conclusion of Michelson and Morley's experiment would de facto no longer be the absence of a luminiferous ether (intended as immobile and isotropic) but that of the existence of a dynamic propagation medium influenced (or potentially influencing as we will see later) by the movement of our planet.

This hypothesis was notably promoted by Georges Stokes and then refuted, notably due to the phenomenon of stellar aberration (the position of the stars in the sky seen from the earth describes a mini ellipse during the seasons due to the speed of rotation of the earth around the sun): this aberration can very well be explained, if we admit, unlike G. Stokes, that the movement of ether only accompanies the earth very locally and that the major part of the luminous path made between the stars and the earth is mostly done within a relatively immobile ether (compared to the movement of the earth).

This moving medium (like river water) would therefore serve as a medium for the propagation of light and more generally electromagnetic waves without resorting to the abstraction constituted by photons.

Extension to gravity modeling:

Here is a second area that has been remarkably well modeled mathematically since Newton but that is quite inexplicable from a phenomenological point of view: two masses attract each other depending on their weights and the distance separating them: calculation makes it possible to measure this force of attraction but in no way to explain it.

Let us return to the dynamic flow of ether mentioned previously and suppose it moves centripetal towards the center of each mass (and more powerful if the mass is larger). The particles of ether (in essence not observable with light since they serve as a support for its propagation) would permanently bombard all the atoms by "pushing" them towards the center of the largest mass nearby. The sum of these micro-forces would lead to explaining gravity. This force, by concentration of the flow, would increase in $1/r^2$ the closer one gets to the center of mass.

Thus, the effect of this dynamic flow of cosmic source would be at the origin of the movement of all mass, causing gravity but also rotation of the earth in its orbit around the sun (or even the sun within our galaxy).

Incidentally, the centripetal movement of this flow, which supports the propagation of light, could explain other phenomena. Take for example a high-mass star: the light rays emanating from this star would therefore have to go up a very strong opposing flow to escape from the star (like a boat going upstream): This path in an opposing flow would necessarily produce a Doppler effect, shifting the radiated waves towards the red: this could explain the "Red Shift" observed in the radiation of all stars and impact the expansion constant of the universe (in the extreme, this could lead to explaining the expansion of the universe by an optical illusion!).

This centripetal flow could also give physical meaning to gravitational lenses and the Shapiro effect: light would be naturally deflected due to the deformation of its propagation medium caused by the presence of a large mass whose incident radius is almost tangent.

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The Olbers paradox (black sky background) could be explained by a very slight absorption of light waves in the ether (very distant light sources cannot reach us) or by the curvature of the propagation support flux at the periphery of our universe.

Assuming that ether particles do not have zero mass, one could imagine that the sum of their masses corresponds to that of dark matter invoked in certain cosmological models. Similarly, dark energy could be assimilated to the sum of their kinetic energies.

Finally, it could be that black holes are in fact extremely massive bodies causing the ether flux to converge toward their centers at a velocity greater than the speed of light: as a result, light waves could no longer “escape” from this flux, leading to the perception of a black hole.

A potential explanation for the wave/particle duality :

Let us now revisit the phenomena of reflection, refraction and diffraction of light on matter in the light of this flow of support particles.

The very notion of photon is no longer necessary: light is a wave that propagates in the ether, a wave which, upon contact with atoms, collides with their electrons, thus causing changes in electronic orbits and therefore generating waves of colors specific to the energy levels of the electrons concerned. These colors, as waves, are in turn propagated in the flow of ether, each atom behaving as a micro- source of light (therefore of a wave). In this context, only the wave is reflected and the Fresnel- Descartes law is obviously respected, not the flow of ether which, a priori, crosses matter (but which is perhaps slowed down by the collision of its particles against the atoms (a bit like a flow of liquid is slowed down by a filter)). This correlates with the experiments which have been able to demonstrate that the speed of propagation of light is slowed down in water or glass.

On very specific and highly organized atomic structures, notably with crystals, the wave propagates inside the structure and is further refracted due to the modification of its ether-carrying flow, notably its slowing potential, on the surface and in the structure (whose optical refractive index would be linked to this structure which interacts with the ether flow). We can also try to explain the phenomenon of decomposition of light by a prism in this way: each vibration frequency of the wave would be affected differently by the slowing down of the flow of ether in a given medium (e.g. prism), which causes the separation of colors.

Diffraction is also explained here in a classically wave-like manner, due to the perturbation of the wave in the flow of ether by the slit it to be crossed: this results in interference downstream, the ether offering at this microscopic level sufficient spatial coherence although it is in motion. The shadow and interference zones would be the additions and subtractions linked to the layerings of waves in this ether fluid.

We could also ask about the permeability of different materials to ether'waves:

- For the open or regular crystalline structures, as we have just seen: the wave in the etheric flow crosses the interstices of the atomic network without too much disturbance, provided that its frequency does not resonate with the resonance frequency of the material;
- For materials, on the other hand, made up of an amorphous or dense atomic network (as in a metal), the interaction with the wave would cause diffuse disturbances , preventing the passage of the wave (which would explain in particular the non-propagation of electromagnetic waves inside a Faraday cage for example).

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Thus, the etheric permeability of a material would be a function of the resonance between the local vibration frequencies of the material and those of the wave carried by the etheric flow . The weaker the resonance, the more the wave it carries passes without "loss" (transparency):

- Transparency = weak coupling between the oscillations of the ether flow and the structure of the material
- Opacity = strong coupling , hence reflection, absorption or diffusion

And this could explain why some crystals are transparent in certain wavelengths but opaque in others : the electronic structure would not be the only factor at play , there would also be an etheric factor to consider.

Ultimately, the denser the material, the more it interacts with the wave carried by the ether flow: Gases are obviously very permeable, liquids less so and solids very little so (with the exception of crystals): in all cases the wave carried by the ether flow attempts to cross these structures but its propagation speed is affected or even annihilated for most solids. This modification of the propagation speed would be linked to the interaction of the ether flow with the atomic structure of the material.

A possible explanation for quantum entanglement:

Today, we are wondering about the mystery of photonic entanglement: how can two entangled photons keep polarization in a statistically synchronized manner when the distance separating them prevents the possibility of transmitting information without exceeding the speed of light (the famous "spooky action at a distance" mentioned by Einstein)? Various attempts at explanation have been put forward: Do the photons carry an internal hidden variable that they share (a sort of internal memory that would lead them to change state at the same time without communicating) or is it that, as Bohm proposed, there exists a hidden quantum field?

In the model presented here, the very notion of photon no longer really has any meaning: the experiment consists rather in creating a coherent structure of oscillation in the flow of ether, extended over two distinct regions of space: the two structures would flow on the same ether wave produced at their creation. In other words, the two structures vibrate in phase in the ether and this whatever the distance separating them: it is the global structure of the ether on the local scale of the earth which ensures the entanglement observed. There is thus:

- **determination** , but not by local variables
- **consistency** , but not necessarily by chance.

This sheds new light on the EPR paradox (1935: Einstein, Podolsky and Rosen):

- Entanglement comes from the fact that the two "particles" are indeed coherent local oscillations of the same global structure of the ether .

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- When we measure a "particle", we sample its state at time t , which is the same as that measured at the same instant on the other "particle" because they vibrate in phase in the same coherent global medium (without transport of information in the relativistic sense).

So no superluminal communication, just a consistent effect on the same continuous support: This allows:

- To respect Bell's results (violation of inequalities),
- To have an objective reality (the support exists),
- And to get out of the paradox of "instantaneous change at a distance", by interpreting it as a wave coherence of the global etheric support.

A potential and new explanation of the single-photon Young's double-slit experiment:

As a reminder, the experiment consists in generating photons one by one, making them successively pass through two very closely spaced slits, and observing the interference pattern that gradually forms on a downstream screen. It is observed that each photon "ends" its path by forming a dot on the screen at a seemingly random position, but as more photons are sent, the collection of these impact points eventually "draws" the usual interference pattern.

With the ether-based model, the photon does not exist as such; rather, each individual excitation (the event that supposedly creates a photon) generates a wave. This wave propagates, interacts with the medium—particularly with the two slits—and produces a kind of local absorption point on the screen (similar to a wave of higher amplitude, as a statistical byproduct of the noise in the ether medium, due for example to the electromagnetic pollution all around) at a position that seems random but actually reflects the classical interference mode of the wave (consistent with the overall probability density of absorption). The interference thus does not arise from the individual photon but from the underlying wave field.

In the version of this same experiment with entangled photons (such as the delayed choice quantum eraser), entanglement then corresponds to correlated modes of the ether waves (in phase and in energy).

Thus, imposing polarization on one of the slits amounts to shifting the phase orthogonally between the two sub-waves emerging from the slits, and consequently, they no longer recombine: interference fringes naturally do not form. There is therefore no need for a "magical" explanation in which photons somehow "know in advance" that one of the slits will be polarized! In short, the measurement of the chosen path disturbs the propagation of the ether wave and skews the perception of the actual process (as a direct application of Heisenberg's uncertainty principle).

The reappearance of fringes after removing the polarization-induced erasure mentioned above is normal since the system simply returns to its previous state.

Ether and electromagnetic waves:

Let us now analyze how electromagnetic waves could be propagated in this flow of ether. For this we will make the following hypothesis: the ether particles are very small dipoles able to interact with each other forming transversal waves.

Let's start with a radio transmitter: this sets electrons in motion on a conductive medium. This skin current interacts with the ether particles passing through it.

These particles, struck by the moving electrons, collectively start rotating:

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- around a horizontal axis perpendicular to the propagation for the electric field
- around a vertical axis perpendicular to the propagation for the magnetic field

These two rotations are 90° out of phase and of a frequency consistent with the motion of the electrons that caused them.

The ether particles, with no other movement than that of the ether flow which carries them, then propagate their rotations step by step to their neighbors.

Upon reception on a suitable support (conductor for a radio antenna or resonant like a water molecule in a microwave oven), the ether particles in turn strike the electrons in large numbers, setting them in motion and recreating a local current (or for water molecules, heating by resonance).

Thus, the ether would propagate electromagnetic waves just as for light.

Conclusion :

I am fully aware of the intuitive and unproven nature of all of the above. The purpose of this article is to offer a new framework of phenomenological explanation to complement the brilliant, accurate, and verified theories and experiments already in force. It is therefore a question of proposing a debate and proposals for further investigation of this new model: to criticize it, correct it, improve it, or even destroy it if it turns out that it is not verified by experience.

At the experimental level, a first step could be to measure precisely, without correction for quantum and relativistic biases, the travel time of a light ray or a radio wave between a geostationary satellite and its closest point to the Earth at the equator: We could thus deduce whether the outward travel time is different from the return travel time and estimate the speed of the centripetal ether flow at the equator.

Finally, I am perfectly aware of the many limitations of the model: for example, what is (are) the source(s) of this flow of ether or where does this flow of ether come out once it has reached the center of a mass? ...